

The Potential of Tutoring in Higher Education: Students' Preferences, Consumption, and the Role of Information

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Summary

1. This study estimates the preferences, perceptions and consumption of tutoring among 1,200 Flemish first-year higher education students using a discrete choice experiment.
2. Students' willingness-to-pay for tutoring is large, as they see it as highly effective at improving their educational outcomes.
3. Demand for tutoring is higher among students from low socioeconomic backgrounds, but they are less able to afford private tutoring.
4. Only 8% of students purchase private tutoring. High costs, limited supply, and behavioral biases like status quo concerns likely explain this. Correcting students' biased views on education returns has little effect on their willingness to pay for tutoring.
5. Public investments in tutoring could increase social welfare and social mobility cost-effectively, while lowering barriers to students seeking academic support.

1. Introduction

Most higher education students in OECD countries do not graduate within the prescribed duration of their bachelor's program, and more than 1 in 5 fails to graduate at all (OECD, 2022). This imposes significant costs on students and society. Tutoring, defined as supplemental course-specific instruction, either individual or in smaller groups, is a highly effective intervention to improve higher education

outcomes (Gordanier et al., 2019; Hardt et al., 2023). However, little is known about the demand for tutoring programs, their optimal design, or cost-effectiveness (Kraft & Falken, 2021). Moreover, while private tutoring is well researched in K-12 education given its threat to social mobility (Byun et al., 2018), very little research exists on the consumption of private tutoring in higher education.

In De Cort & De Witte (2024) we estimate the preferences, perceptions and consumption of tutoring for 1,200 Flemish first-year higher

education students using a discrete choice experiment. We then use these results to simulate the cost-effectiveness and welfare gains of different tutoring programs. Finally, we examine private tutoring consumption and whether students underinvest due to informational biases.

2. Methodology

To examine our research questions, we distributed a survey containing a discrete choice experiment, questions about the perceived effectiveness and consumption of tutoring, and an information experiment. Our sample consists of more than 1,200 Flemish first-year students from two universities of applied sciences and one research university.

In our discrete choice experiment, students repeatedly choose between two different tutoring packages as well as the option to follow no tutoring (see Figure 1). The tutoring packages differ by amount, tutor, class size and price. Students' also rate how much they believe these tutoring programs would improve their educational outcomes. Analyzing the responses allows us to precisely quantify students' preferences for tutoring and their perception of its effectiveness. We also measure how many students purchase tutoring on the private market.

In the information experiment, we assess how providing information about the potential returns to tutoring increases students' preferences for tutoring. To do so, we conduct a Randomized Control Trial (RCT) experiment where we randomly select some students to receive this information and then compare their preferences with those who did not receive the extra information.

Finally, we simulate the cost-effectiveness of different tutoring programs. To do so, we

combine the estimates of students' preferences and perceptions of the effectiveness of tutoring with baseline estimates of the cost of tutoring program and the social returns to increasing the share of students that graduate (in time). We extensively consider the sensitivity of our results to the assumed costs and returns.

3. Results

1. Preferences and perceptions of tutoring

We find that most students have a sizeable willingness-to-pay for tutoring as they perceive it to be highly effective at increasing their educational attainment. As willingness-to-pay (WTP) we consider the maximum price an individual is willing to pay for a good or service. However, students' willingness-to-pay for having an experienced lecturer and smaller class sizes is limited (see Figure 2). Finally, female students, students without a higher-educated father, and students with a lower GPA have a stronger preference for tutoring.

2. Welfare analysis and the optimal design of a tutoring program

First, we estimate that a tutoring program in small groups of 8 to 12 students taught by an older student is the most cost-effective way to provide this tutoring. Second, we estimate that the returns of such a tutoring program both for the individual student and for society are significantly larger than its costs. This result remains robust even if the returns are five times lower than estimated and the costs three times larger than estimated.

3. Consumption of private tutoring and the role of information

We find that 8% of our sample pays for private tutoring, though with significant

heterogeneity between institutions and study programs. Students with a father without a higher education degree are less likely to pay for private tutoring, despite their stronger preference for tutoring as highlighted by the choice experiment.

Given the sizeable willingness-to-pay for tutoring, one might expect consumption of private tutoring to be more prevalent. We discuss three possible reasons for this discrepancy. First, students might underinvest in tutoring due to behavioral biases such as status-quo bias or concerns about their social image. Second, private providers mostly offer one-on-one tutoring. They might lack the scale to provide group lessons which would better match students' demand. Finally, we find no evidence that students overstated their willingness-to-pay. We estimate that, given students' own perception of the effectiveness of tutoring, students' willingness-to-pay should in fact be higher. Students underestimate the returns to education in the experiment, but correcting this bias only slightly increases their willingness-to-pay.

4. Policy implications

1. Monitor the prevalence of private tutoring

Private tutoring in Flemish higher education is relatively common, yet access remains unequal, posing a risk to social mobility. Despite its significance, few countries systematically track the consumption private tutoring, particularly in tertiary education (Bray, 2024). We recommend that education systems regularly monitor the prevalence to better understand its impact and address potential inequalities.

2. Investments in optimal tutoring programs might be cost-effective and increase social mobility

Our findings indicate that the private and social returns to tutoring programs can far exceed their costs. For example, expanding Teaching Assistantship sessions or peer tutoring programs holds strong potential to improve student outcomes cost-effectively. Given the unequal access to private tutoring, providing a robust public alternative could reduce reliance on the private tutoring market and therefore promote social mobility (Bray, 2024).

3. Continue to evaluate new and existing tutoring programs

While our results as well as earlier findings on the (cost-)effectiveness of tutoring are encouraging, more research is needed. For example, little is known about the role of class size in tutoring's effectiveness. Additionally, the effectiveness of such programs seems to diminish when adopted at scale (Kraft et al., 2024). Policymakers and higher education institutions seeking to expand tutoring should prioritize rigorous evaluation to ensure that these specific programs are (cost-)effective.

What is EFFECT ?

EFFECT is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

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Figures

Figure 1. Example of a choice set from the discrete choice experiment (source: De Cort & De Witte, 2024).

Below you again find **two tutoring programs** that differ by four characteristics. You can assume that all characteristics not shown (such as the location) are identical. You can also opt to follow **no tutoring**.

Program A	Program B
4 hours of tutoring per week	3 hours of tutoring per week
Taught by an experienced lecturer	Taught by an senior student
In a group of 12 students	In a group of 24 students
Price of €25 per hour	Price of €20 per hour

Which option is your

first choice? Program A Program B No tutoring

second choice? Program A Program B No tutoring

Figure 2. Average Willingness-To-Pay (WTP) for different tutoring packages (De Cort & De Witte, 2024)

Notes: WTP estimates are derived from the mean coefficients of the mixed logit analysis of the discrete choice experiment using main effects, as reported in Supplementary Table 3. 95% confidence intervals are estimated using the delta method. UAS refers to the subsample of university of applied science students, while RU refers to the subsample of research university students

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